

TactScribe: A Wearable Fingertip Sensor for Vibrotactile Data Collection via Natural Stroking

Reina Hanzawa¹, Michikuni Eguchi^{1,2}, Kenichi Mori³, Miku Nonogaki³,
Masanori Morita³, and Takefumi Hiraki^{1,2}

¹ University of Tsukuba, Ibaraki, Japan

{hanzawa, eguchi, hiraki}@mvmml.slis.tsukuba.ac.jp

² Cluster Metaverse Lab, Tokyo, Japan

³ Murata Manufacturing Co., Ltd., Kyoto, Japan

{kenichi_mori, m.nonogaki4hm, masanori.morita}@murata.com

Abstract. Vibrotactile information obtained through fingertip contact is expected to enable various applications. However, existing recording systems rely on specialized instruments and wired connections, making it difficult to collect tactile data through natural human behavior. In this study, we propose a wearable tactile recording system that combines a small, flexible sensor worn on the fingertip with a wireless transmission system for sensor data. Using the proposed system, we collected vibrotactile data from five types of materials and conducted material classification experiments with machine learning. The results achieved 83.2% overall accuracy, demonstrating that the recorded data contains sufficient tactile information for material classification and suggesting the system’s potential for diverse vibrotactile dataset construction.

Keywords: Wearable computing · Tactile sensing · Haptic texture

1 Introduction

Touch is an important sense for identifying the material and surface texture of objects. Vibrotactile information generated by stroking a material with the fingertip is known to be directly involved in the perception of properties such as hardness and surface fineness. By recording and accumulating such tactile information as digital data, several applications become possible, including material identification and haptic texture search.

Prior work on tactile data recording has relied on various specialized instruments. Eguchi et al. [1] developed a system that automatically collects large numbers of tactile samples using a robotic mechanism; however, its mechanical constraints limited data collection to linear motion patterns. A(touch)ment [3] records vibrotactile data via a tactile microphone wired to a smartphone’s audio jack, while Twech [2] measures vibrotactile signals by pressing a smartphone-connected rod-shaped probe against a material surface. In all these cases, the recording procedure departs from the natural touching behavior of everyday human interactions, limiting the user’s physical freedom during data collection.

Fig. 1: Overview of the wearable tactile recording system.

To address this limitation, we propose a wearable tactile recording system in which a piezoelectric film sensor is attached directly to the fingertip, enabling data collection via natural stroking motions with Bluetooth wireless transmission. As a preliminary evaluation, we conducted material classification on five materials, achieving 83.2% overall accuracy with ResNet34.

2 Wearable Tactile Recording System

Figure 1 presents an overview of the wearable vibrotactile recording system developed in this study. This system is designed to measure vibrations transmitted through the fingertips during tactile interactions. It comprises a fingertip sensor unit and a wrist-worn data logger.

At each fingertip, a piezoelectric film sensor (PicoleafTM, Murata Manufacturing Co., Ltd.), was mounted on a finger stall fabricated via 3D printing. The sensor signal was conditioned through an I/V conversion circuit and an amplification circuit, and subsequently acquired as a digital signal via an analog-to-digital converter integrated in a microcomputer (M5StickC Plus; M5Stack). A microcomputer was secured to the wrist using a strap, and the data transmitted from the fingertip sensors was continuously streamed to a host PC (THIRD-WAVE 4CZ59) via Bluetooth. The sampling rate was set to 1000 Hz, covering the vibrotactile frequency band relevant to surface texture perception.

3 Experiments

To verify that the tactile data collected by our system contains sufficient discriminative information, we conducted a material classification experiment.

One participant stroked each of the five materials used in the Cluster Tactile Texture Dataset [1] (Jute, Mesh, Metal, Plastic, Wood) 30 times, randomly varying stroking speed, direction, and applied force. Signals were segmented into non-overlapping 1-second windows and split into training, validation, and test sets (7:1:2). Each window was converted to a 128-band log-mel spectrogram (Hann window, $N_{\text{fft}} = 256$), replicated to three channels, and used to fine-tune an ImageNet-pretrained ResNet34 end-to-end, classifying into five material categories via a fully connected layer. Training used AdamW ($\text{lr}=10^{-3}$) with

Fig. 2: Confusion matrix and per-material accuracy of the classification result.

cross-entropy loss, averaged over five random-seed runs on the same host PC used for recording.

The confusion matrix with per-material accuracy is shown in Fig. 2. The overall accuracy was 83.2%, demonstrating that the collected tactile signals contain sufficient material discriminative information. Metal achieved the highest accuracy, while Jute and Wood showed relatively low accuracy, reflecting the perceptual similarity between fibrous and organic textures.

4 Conclusion, Open Research Questions, and Interdisciplinary Exchange

In this study, we proposed a wearable vibrotactile recording system using a fingertip-mounted piezoelectric film sensor with Bluetooth wireless transmission, enabling data collection through natural stroking motions with minimal physical constraints. A five-material classification experiment using ResNet34 achieved 83.2% overall accuracy, confirming that the recorded signals contain sufficient discriminative tactile information.

Future work includes co-recording motion parameters, multi-sensor fingertip configurations, and expanding participant diversity. Whether the recorded data appropriately reflects human tactile perception remains an open question; we welcome collaboration with tactile psychophysicists and materials scientists.

References

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